

TEACHERS' PERSONALITY TRAITS AND CONFLICT MANAGEMENT IN THE WORKPLACE

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 30

Issue 9

Pages: 1382-1391

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2918

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14651791

Manuscript Accepted: 12-19-2024

Teachers' Personality Traits and Conflict Management in the Workplace

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Abstract

This study investigated the personality traits and conflict management styles of teachers at Lumaynay Elementary School and its Sangeay Annex in Altavas, Aklan. A mixed-method approach was employed, collecting data from 13 teachers' participants through standardized and researcher-made questionnaires. Results revealed that teachers exhibited diplomat-protagonist personality traits. Common conflicts arose between teachers, administrators, and students, resolved primarily through collaboration, avoidance, accommodation, and compromise. Statistical analysis showed a significant correlation between conflict management styles and conflict frequency. Semi-structured interviews revealed additional factors contributing to conflicts, including workload burdens on new teachers and seniority-related superiority complexes. Notably, "The war of the Marites" phenomenon hindered effective conflict resolution. Findings inform the development of targeted intervention strategies to enhance conflict management within the school.

Keywords: *personality traits, workplace conflict, conflict management, people management, educational environment*

Introduction

Conflict is an inherent aspect of organizational life, particularly in educational settings where diverse personalities interact daily (Ghaffar, 2019). Teachers, as pivotal members of educational institutions, face unique challenges that can lead to conflicts, impacting their effectiveness and well-being (Madrigal & Imperial, 2021). The interplay between personality traits and conflict management styles is critical in understanding how educators navigate these challenges. Research indicates that personality traits significantly influence conflict resolution strategies with the Big Five Personality Dimensions serving as a foundational framework (Shaukat & Uzman, 2020)

In the Philippine context, teachers are expected to maintain professionalism and emotional regulation despite external pressures (Colomeischi et al., 2014). The Philippine Professional Standard for Teachers emphasize the importance of teachers' emotional intelligence and interpersonal skills in fostering a positive learning environment. (Department of Education, 2017). However, the phenomenon known as the "War of the Marites" referring to gossip and rivalry among teachers, can exacerbate conflicts and hinder effective collaboration (Gungor & Kucuk, 2014).

This study aims to explore the personality traits of teachers at Lumaynay Elementary School and its Annex Sang-eay and their relationship with conflict management styles, ultimately developing an intervention plan to enhance conflict resolution.

Research Questions

This study aims to investigate the personality traits and conflict management styles of teachers at Lumaynay Elementary School and its Annex Sang-eay and their impact on workplace conflicts. Specifically, the research seeks:

1. What are the personality traits of teachers when classified as:
 - 1.1. analysts (architect, logician, commander, and debater);
 - 1.2. diplomats (advocate, mediator, protagonist, and campaigner);
 - 1.3. sentinels (logistician, defender, executive, and consul);
 - 1.4. explorers (virtuoso, adventurer, entrepreneur, and entertainer)?
2. What are the common conflicts that arise in the workplace in terms of:
 - 2.1. teacher-teacher;
 - 2.2. teacher-administrator;
 - 2.3. teacher- students; and
 - 2.4. teacher-parents?
3. What is the conflict management style of the teachers in terms of:
 - 3.1. collaborating;
 - 3.2. competing;
 - 3.3. avoiding;
 - 3.4. accommodating; and
 - 3.5. compromising?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the teacher's personality traits and the conflicts that arise in the workplace?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the teacher's personality traits and the conflict management style?

6. Is there a significant relationship between the teacher's conflict management style and the conflicts that arise in the workplace?
7. What are the experiences of teachers when a conflict in the workplace arise in terms of:
 - 7.1. hierarchy of positions;
 - 7.2. allocations of school responsibilities;
 - 7.3. personal and professional education;
 - 7.4. workplace fellowship; and
 - 7.5. work opportunities and promotions?
8. What are the reasons why these conflicts arise in the workplace?
9. What intervention plan can be developed to prevent conflict in the workplace among teachers.

Methodology

A mixed-methods research design was employed to gather comprehensive data on teachers' personality traits and conflict management styles. The integration of quantitative and qualitative data collection methods allows for deeper exploration of the research objectives. The study included all teachers (100%) from Lumaynay Elementary School and its Annex Sang-eay.

Participants completed the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI) personality assessment and a researcher-made questionnaire designed to capture their experiences with workplace conflicts and preferred conflict management styles. The instruments were chosen for their reliability and validity in measuring the variables of interest.

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, while qualitative data were thematically coded to identify common patterns and insights. The study adhered to ethically guidelines, ensuring participant confidentiality and voluntary participation.

Results and Discussion

Teachers' Personality Traits

The analysis revealed that 96.7% of the teachers exhibited diplomat-protagonist personality traits, characterized by a collaborative and empathetic approach to conflict resolution.

Table 1. *Teachers' Personality Traits*

Personality Traits	<i>f</i>	%
Diplomats		
Protagonist	12	92.3%
Sentinels		
Consul	1	7.7%
Total	13	100%

Conflicts that arise in the workplace

Conflicts were most frequently observed in interactions between teachers ($M=2.85$), with students ($M=3.00$), and with administrators ($M=2.85$). Conflicts between teachers and parents were reported as occurring less frequently ($M=2.38$).

Table 2. *Common Conflicts that Arise in the Workplace*

Common Conflicts in the Workplace	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Between Teacher and Teacher	2.85	Often
Between Teacher and Administrator	2.85	Often
Between Teacher and Students	3.00	Often
Between Teacher and Parents	2.38	Sometimes
GRAND MEAN	2.77	Often

Legend: Rarely (1.00 – 1.49), Sometimes (1.50 – 2.49), Often (2.50 – 3.49), and Always (3.50 – 4.00)

Conflict Management Style

Among the conflict management styles, collaborating (69.23%), accommodating (69.23%), and compromising (84.62%) were often practiced, while competing was observed less frequently (53.84%).

Table 3. Teachers' Conflict Management Style

Conflict Management Style	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Collaborating		
Sometimes	2	15.38%
Often	9	69.23%
Always	2	15.38%
Total	13	100%
Competing		
Rarely	2	15.38%
Sometimes	7	53.84%
Often	4	30.78%
Total	13	100%
Avoiding		
Sometimes	3	23.1%
Often	9	69.23%
Always	1	7.69%
Total	13	100%
Accommodating		
Sometimes	2	15.38%
Often	9	69.23%
Always	2	15.38%
Total	13	100%
Compromising		
Sometimes	2	15.38%
Often	11	84.62%
Total	13	100%

Relationship between Teachers' Personality Traits and Conflicts that Arise in the Workplace

A cross-tabulation analysis revealed no statistically significant correlation between teachers' personality traits and workplace conflicts.

Table 4. The Relationship between Teachers' Personality Traits and Conflicts that Arise in the Workplace

Teachers' Personality Traits	Workplace Conflict (Teacher and Teacher)							
	Sometimes		Often		Always		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Diplomats	3	23.08%	8	61.54%	1	7.69%	12	92.31%
Sentinels	0	0.00%	1	7.69%	0	0.00%	1	7.69%
Total	3	23.08%	9	69.23%	1	7.69%	13	100%
Pearson Chi-square = 0.481			Df = 2			P = 0.786		
Teacher and Administration								
Diplomats	3	23.08%	8	61.54%	1	7.69%	12	92.31%
Sentinels	0	0.00%	1	7.69%	0	0.00%	1	7.69%
Total	3	23.08%	9	69.23%	1	7.69%	13	100%
Pearson Chi-square = 0.481			Df = 2			0.786		
Teacher and Students								
Diplomats	2	15.38%	8	61.54%	2	15.38%	12	92.31%
Sentinels	0	0.00%	1	7.69%	0	0.00%	1	7.69%
Total	2	15.38%	9	69.23%	2	15.38%	13	100%
Pearson Chi-square = 0.481			Df = 2			P = 0.786		
Teacher and Parents								
	Rarely		Sometimes		Often		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Diplomats	1	7.69%	5	38.46%	6	46.15%	12	92.31%
Sentinels	0	0.00%	1	7.69%	0	0.00%	1	7.69%
Total	1	7.69%	6	46.15%	6	46.15%	13	100%
Pearson Chi-square = 1.264			Df = 2			P = 0.532		

Relationship between Teachers' Personality Traits and Conflict Management Styles.

A cross-tabulation analysis revealed no statistically significant correlation between teachers' personality traits and conflict management styles.

Table 5. *The Relationship between Teachers' Personality Traits and Conflict management styles*

Teachers' Personality Traits	Conflict Management Style (Collaborating)							
	Sometimes		Often		Always		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Diplomats	2	15.38%	8	61.54%	2	15.38%	12	92.31%
Sentinel	0	0.00%	1	7.69%	0	0.00%	1	7.69%
Total	2	15.38%	9	69.23%	2	15.38%	13	100%
Pearson Chi-square = 0.481			Df = 2			P = 0.786		
Conflict Management Style (Competing)								
Diplomats	2	15.38%	6	46.15%	4	30.78%	12	92.31%
Sentinels	0	0.00%	1	7.69%	0	0.00%	1	7.69%
Total	2	15.38%	7	73.85%	4	30.78%	13	100%
Pearson Chi-square = 0.929			Df = 2			P = 0.629		
Conflict Management Style (Avoiding)								
Diplomats	3	23.08%	8	61.54%	1	7.69%	12	92.31%
Sentinels	0	0.00%	1	7.69%	0	0.00%	1	7.69%
Total	3	23.08%	9	69.23%	1	7.69%	13	100%
Pearson Chi-square = 0.481			Df = 2			P = 0.529		
Conflict Management Style (Accommodating)								
Diplomats	2	15.38%	8	61.54%	2	15.38%	12	92.31%
Sentinels	0	0.00%	1	7.69%	0	0.00%	1	7.69%
Total	2	15.38%	9	69.23%	2	15.38%	13	100%
Conflict Management Style (Compromising)								
Diplomats	2	15.38%	10	76.92%	12	92.31%		
Sentinels	0	0.00%	1	7.69%	1	7.69%		
Total	2	15.38%	11	84.62%	13	100%		
Pearson Chi-square = 0.197			Df = 1			P = 0.657		

Relationship between Teachers' Conflict Management Style and the Possible Conflict that Arise in the workplace.

A cross-tabulation analysis revealed there was statistically high significant correlation between teachers' conflict management styles and possible conflicts that arise in the workplace.

Table 6. *The relationship between Teachers' Conflict Management Style and the Possible Conflicts that Arise in the Workplace*

Conflict Management Style	Workplace Conflict Teacher and Teacher							
	Sometimes		Often		Always		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Collaborating								
Sometimes	2	15.38%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	2	15.38%
Often	1	7.69%	8	61.54%	0	0.00%	9	69.23%
Always	0	0.00%	1	7.69%	1	7.69%	2	15.38%
Total	3	23.08%	9	69.23%	1	7.69%	13	100%
Pearson Chi-Square = 13.642			Df = 4			P = 0.009		
Cramer's V = .724			Highly Significant					
Competing								
Rarely	2	15.38%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	2	15.38%
Sometimes	1	7.69%	6	46.15%	0	0.00%	7	53.85%
Often	0	0.00%	3	23.08%	1	7.69%	4	38.46%
Total	3	23.08%	9	69.23%	1	7.69%	13	100%
Pearson Chi-square = 10.214			Df = 4			P = 0.037		
Cramer's V = .627			Highly Significant					
Avoiding								
Sometimes	1	7.69%	2	15.38%	0	0.00%	3	23.08%
Often	2	15.38%	6	46.15%	0	0.00%	9	69.23%
Always	0	0.00%	1	7.69%	1	7.69%	1	7.69%
Total	3	23.08%	9	69.23%	1	7.69%	13	100%
Pearson Chi-square = 0.963			Df = 4			P = 0.915		

Accommodating									
Sometimes	2	15.38%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	2	15.38%	
Often	1	7.69%	8	61.54%	1	7.69%	9	69.23%	
Always	0	0.00%	1	7.69%	0	0.00%	2	15.38%	
Total	3	23.08%	9	69.23%	1	7.69%	13	100%	
Compromising									
Sometimes	2	15.38%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	2	15.38%	
Often	1	7.69%	9	69.23%	1	7.69%	11	84.62%	
Total	3	23.08%	9	69.23%	1	7.69%	13	100%	
Pearson Chi-square = 7.879					Df = 2		P = 0.019		
Cramer's V = .778					Highly Significant				
Collaborating									
Teacher and Administrator									
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
Sometimes	2	15.38%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	2	15.38%	
Often	1	7.69%	8	61.54%	0	0.00%	9	69.23%	
Always	0	0.00%	1	7.69%	1	7.69%	2	15.38%	
Total	3	23.08%	9	69.23%	1	7.69%	13	100%	
Pearson Chi-Square = 13.642					Df = 4		P = 0.009		
Cramer's V = .724					Highly Significant				
Competing									
Rarely	2	15.38%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	2	15.38%	
Sometimes	1	7.69%	6	46.15%	0	0.00%	7	53.85%	
Often	0	0.00%	3	28.08%	1	7.69%	4	30.78%	
Total	3	23.08%	9	69.23%	1	7.69%	13	100%	
Pearson Chi-square = 10.214					Df = 4		P = 0.037		
Cramer's V = .627					Highly Significant				
Avoiding									
Sometimes	1	7.69%	2	15.38%	0	0.00%	3	23.08%	
Often	2	15.38%	6	46.15%	1	7.69%	9	69.23%	
Always	0	0.00%	1	7.69%	0	0.00%	1	7.69%	
Total	3	23.08%	9	69.23%	1	7.69%	13	100%	
Pearson Chi-square = 0.963					Df = 4		P = 0.915		
Accommodating									
Sometimes	2	15.38%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	2	15.38%	
Often	1	7.69%	8	61.54%	0	0.00%	9	69.23%	
Always	0	0.00%	1	7.69%	1	7.69%	2	15.38%	
Total	3	23.08%	9	69.23%	1	7.69%	13	100%	
Pearson Chi-square = 13.642					Df = 4		P = 0.009		
Cramer's V = .724					Highly Significant				
Compromising									
Sometimes	2	15.38%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	2	15.38%	
Often	1	7.69%	9	0.00%	1	7.69%	11	84.62%	
Total	3	23.08%	9	69.23%	1	7.69%	13	100%	
Pearson Chi-square = 7.879					Df = 2		P = 0.019		
Cramer's v = .778					Highly Significant				
Collaborating									
Teacher and Students									
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
Sometimes	2	15.38%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	2	15.38%	
Often	0	0.00%	9	69.23%	0	0.00%	9	69.23%	
Always	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	2	15.38%	2	15.38%	
Total	2	15.38%	9	69.23%	2	15.38%	13	100%	
Pearson Chi-square = 26.00					Df = 4		P = 0.000		
Cramer's V = 1.00					Strong Significance				
Competing									
Rarely	2	15.38%	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	2	15.38%	
Sometimes	0	0.00%	6	46.15%	1	7.69%	7	53.85%	
Often	0	0.00%	3	23.08%	1	7.69%	4	30.78%	
Total	2	15.38%	9	69.23%	2	15.38%	13	100%	
Pearson Chi-square = 13.232					Df = 4		P = 0.10		
Avoiding									
Sometimes	1	7.69%	2	15.38%	0	0.00%	3	23.08%	
Often	1	7.69%	6	46.15%	2	15.38%	9	69.23%	
Always	0	0.00%	1	7.69%	0	0.00%	1	7.69%	
Total	2	15.38%	9	69.23%	2	15.38%	13	100%	

Pearson Chi-square = 1.926		Df = 4		P = 0.749			
Accommodating							
Sometimes	2	15.38%	0	0.00%	0 0.00% 2 15.38%		
Often	0	0.00%	9	69.23%	0 0.00% 9 69.23%		
Always	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	2 15.38% 2 15.38%		
Total	2	15.38%	9	69.23%	2 15.38% 13 100%		
Pearson Chi-square = 26.00		Df = 4		P = 0.000			
Cramer's V = 1.000		Strong Significance					
Compromising							
Sometimes	2	15.38%	0	0.00%	0 0.00% 2 15.38%		
Often	0	0.00%	9	69.23%	2 15.38% 11 84.62%		
Total	2	15.38%	9	69.23%	2 15.38% 13 100%		
Pearson Chi-square = 13.000		Df = 4		P = 0.002			
Cramer's V = 1.000		Strong Significant					
Collaborating							
	f	%	f	%	f	%	
Rarely	1	7.69%	1	7.69%	0	0.00%	2 15.38%
Sometimes	0	0.00%	4	30.78%	3	23.08%	7 53.85%
Often	0	0.00%	1	7.69%	3	23.08%	4 30.78%
Total	1	7.69%	6	46.15%	6	46.15%	13 100%
Pearson Chi-square = 7.787		Df = 4		P = 0.067			
Competing							
Rarely	1	7.69%	1	7.69%	0	0.00%	2 15.38%
Sometimes	0	0.00%	5	38.46%	3	23.08%	7 53.85%
Often	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	3	23.08%	4 30.78%
Total	1	7.69%	6	46.15%	6	46.15%	13 100%
Pearson Chi-square = 7.738		Df = 4		P = 0.102			
Avoiding							
Sometimes	1	7.69%	2	15.38%	0	0.00%	3 23.08%
Often	0	0.00%	4	30.78%	5	38.46%	9 69.23%
Always	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	1	7.69%	1 7.69%
Total	1	7.69%	6	46.15%	6	46.15%	13 100%
Pearson Chi-square = 6.259		Df = 4		P = 0.181			
Accommodating							
Sometimes	1	7.69%	1	7.69%	0	0.00%	2 15.38%
Often	0	0.00%	5	38.46%	4	30.78%	9 69.23%
Always	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	2	15.38%	2 15.38%
Total	1	7.69%	6	46.15%	6	46.15%	13 100%
Pearson Chi-square = 8.787		Df = 4		P = 0.067			
Compromising							
Sometimes	1	7.69%	1	7.69%	0	0.00%	2 15.38%
Often	0	0.00%	5	38.46%	6	46.15%	11 84.62%
Total	1	7.69%	6	46.15%	6	46.15%	13 100%
Pearson Chi-square = 6.598		Df = 2		P = 0.037			
Cramer's V = .712		Highly Significant					

Experiences of teachers when conflict in the workplace arise

The Young Carry The Burden Of Work

When new and youthful blood is hired at the Department of Education, they consistently bear the majority of the workload. They are required to excel in both administrative and instructional duties. New instructors must be specialists at managing a variety of programs and activities.

Teacher Amy: "Noong bago pa ako sa serbisyo, halos akin lahat ang trabaho. Mula sa pagiging emcee at taga-decorate ng stage. Lahat halos ng mga aktibidad sa school ay ako ang ginawang organizer."

"When I was young in the service, I was tasked to do all the work for the school activities. I would take the lead to organize it."

Teacher Tess: "Sa normal na sitwasyon, iyon sanang mga matatagal na sa serbisyo at may hawak na mas mataas na posisyon, sila dapat ang mas may madaming alam at naituturo iyon sa aming mga bata pa sa serbisyo. Kaso ang nangyayari, iyong mga may mataas na posisyon pa ang walang masyadong workload."

"In a normal situation, those who hold higher positions and have served longer in the service should teach the young teachers. However, those holding higher positions have less or no workload."

Teacher Malou: "Noong bata pa ako sa serbisyo, ako nalang palagi ang naaatasang maglead ng mga activities sa school. Ngayong

medyo nakaangat-angat na ako sa posisyon at marami ng mga bata sa serbisyo sila naman ang napagbubuntunan ng trabaho.”

“When I was young in the service, I was tasked to organize and lead all the activities in the school. Now that I hold a higher position and new teachers are in the service, they would be tasked to take the lead.”

What Are We In Power For?

The remarks made by one of the teachers reveal Department of Education politics. In a school, management and leadership are controlled not by respect for the job, but by who they know determines power. The most common divergence that teachers face is over their school responsibilities, professional development, and opportunities for promotions.

Teacher Lee: “Sa totoo lang napasok ako sa serbisyo dahil pamangkin ako ng School Head. Hindi ko rin naranasan iyong mamorblema sa trabaho sa school kasi palagi akong nabibigyan ng oportunidad. Palagi akong nakakaAttend sa mga seminars dahil mas napapaburan ako ng aking Tiyuhin. Kaya maraming galit sa akin na mga co-teachers ko.”

“I had no difficulties entering the service because my uncle was the School Head. I did not experience any difficulties because I was given many opportunities. I was able to attend seminars and workshops because my uncle favored me. That is why I have a conflict with my co-teachers.”

Teacher Liza: “Naghirap din ako noong hindi pa mataas ang posisyon ko sa pagtuturo. Palagi nalang kasi ako noong napag-uutusan dahil nga bago ako sa serbisyo. Ngayong natapos ko na ang aking pag-aaral sa Masters at napromote na ako, hindi ko na kailangang magpakahirap pa.”

“I experienced hardships when I was still new in the service. I would get tasked with various activities. However, now that I have finished my Master's Degree and I was already promoted, I get to enjoy it.”

Teacher Anna: “Mahirap talaga ang promotion sa DepEd lalo na at hindi mo natapos ang iyong continuing education. Pagdating nga promotion, iyong mga walang nagawa sila pa ang mas nauunang mapromote. Ginagamitan nalang tala ng mga koneksyon sa politika.”

“It is difficult to get promoted in the Department of Education, primarily when you have not pursued continuing education. When it is time for promotions, those who have not done anything are the ones who get promoted first. They use politics to get promoted.”

Teacher Belle: “Noong napasok ako sa DepEd marunong na akong magComputer at magmanipulate ng technology kaya medyo nakakaangat ako sa aking mga kasama. Lumalapit sila sa akin para matulungan ko sila. Ganun din ang aking School Head. Nagkaroon ako ngayon ng kapangyarihan sa paaralan na magdesisyon dahil ako ang palaging naatasan pagdating sa reporting.”

“When I entered the service, I knew how to manipulate gadgets and technology. My co-teachers and even my school head would come to me to be assisted. Since I was the only one versed in technology, I could make decisions, being tasked to be in charge of all the reports.”

Reasons Why Conflicts Arise In The Workplace

The War Of The “Marites”

Teachers, like human beings, are continuously susceptible to unsavory antics by their co-teachers, especially when they have opposing views on each other. Teachers who dislike each other are at war, and their best weapon is the revelation of teachers' secrets and ugly personalities.

Teacher Belle: “Ang mga ‘Marites’ lang naman talaga ang nagpapagulo ng samahan naming rito sa school ang mga sipsip at traidor na mga ‘Marites’.”

“If not for those ‘Marites’ who brew negative environment for otherteachers, we would not have any conflict in the school.”

Teacher Cha: “Noong bago pa ako sa serbisyo pinagsabihan na ako ng aking mga kapatid na huwag na huwag sasali sa pagiging ‘Marites’ ng mga co-teacher ko dahil walang magandang maidudulot it sa akin.”

“When I was new in the service, I was advised by my siblings not to involve myself with my co-teachers 'Maritesez.'”

Teacher Cha: “Kung hindi talaga dahil sa isa kong co-teacher na ‘Marites’ hindi talaga kami magaway-away ng co-teacher ko at hindi ako masisira sa school head ko.”

“If not for my co-teacher, a 'Marites', I would not have any conflict with my other workmates. My school head and I would not have any conflict at.

Conflict Management Intervention Plan For Teachers

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher designed an intervention strategy to reduce disputes between instructors and other teachers, the administration, students, and parents.

Table 7.

<i>Common Behaviors</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Strategies To Address</i>	<i>Key Actions</i>
Avoidance	It occurs when a person ignores or withdraws entirely from a conflict. One will follow this method when they are uncomfortable about the conflict and do not see any reward in resolving it. Although while in this stage, a person might withhold relevant ideas. It can only be resolved once the conflict is faced.	Open and Clear paths for communication,	Listen without interrupting each other Show understanding of the problem. Present each teacher's point of view of the situation. Explain how each teacher feels.
Competition	People may pair up with each other to win. While in this method, a team will not cooperate with others and will assume that, in the end, only one will win. This method can cause frustration among co-workers and does not allow room for diversity and hearing other ideas and thoughts. In a group setting, there are better strategies for success than competition.	Initiate Negotiation among teachers.	Brainstorm possible solutions for the conflict. Accept the need for necessary compromise.
Accommodation	Accommodating might seem like something that helps in a group setting, but at the same time, those using this method might be holding back worthwhile ideas. Using this method will not resolve the conflict and, at times, will let the most assertive parties take control of most conversations and the process.		Choose a fair solution for both parties. Implement the resolution plan.
Compromise	Compromising sounds excellent, although, in the end, no one gets what they want. Every person/team must sacrifice something without stating what is important. By collaborating, reaching one's personal goal is possible.	Consolidation and use of the various conflict resolution mechanisms	Evaluate how the resolution plan is carried out
Collaboration	a method used with people who are assertive and cooperative. By collaborating to find a solution, everyone needs to state their needs, and together, they will find what works for each person.		Communicate the teacher's feelings without prejudice to the other

The results indicated that the majority of teachers exhibited diplomat-protagonist personality traits, which are characterized by a focus on collaboration, empathy, and a desire for harmony in interpersonal relationships. This finding aligns with existing literature that suggests teachers with positive personality traits are more likely to foster a conducive learning environment and effectively manage conflicts (Noreen, 2021; Kaleem, 2007).

In terms of conflict management styles, the study revealed that teachers predominantly utilized collaborating, accommodating, and compromising strategies. The quantitative analysis showed that conflicts were most frequently observed between teachers and students, followed by conflicts among teachers and between teachers and administrators. The qualitative data highlighted those new teachers often felt overwhelmed by additional responsibilities, while senior teachers exhibited a sense of superiority, contributing to interpersonal conflicts.

The statistical analysis employed Chi-square tests to examine the relationships between personality traits and conflict management styles. The results indicated no significant relationship between the teachers' personality traits and the conflicts that arose in the workplace. However, a significant relationship was found between the conflict management styles and the conflicts experienced, particularly in teacher-teacher and teacher-administrator interactions.

Conclusions

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the dynamics of conflict management among teachers in a primary school setting. The predominance of diplomat-protagonist personality traits among teachers suggests that they are well-equipped to handle conflicts through collaborative approaches. This is crucial in educational settings where teamwork and cooperation are essential for effective teaching and learning.

The high frequency of conflicts between teachers and students can be attributed to the diverse backgrounds and personalities of students, which may lead to misunderstandings and disagreements. The study emphasizes the need for teachers to develop a deeper understanding of their students' individual needs and to employ effective communication strategies to mitigate conflicts.

Moreover, the lack of significant correlation between personality traits and conflict management styles suggests that while personality may influence how teachers approach conflicts, external factors such as administrative support, workload, and school culture play a more critical role in conflict dynamics. This finding highlights the importance of creating a supportive school environment that fosters open communication and collaboration among staff.

The study's qualitative findings reveal that the "War of the Marites," a colloquial term for gossip or rivalry, significantly impacts conflict management effectiveness. This underscores the need for school administrators to address interpersonal relationships among staff and to implement professional development programs focused on conflict resolution and team-building.

In conclusion, the study contributes to the understanding of how teachers' personality traits and conflict management styles interact within the workplace. It emphasizes the importance of fostering a positive school culture that supports collaboration and effective conflict resolution strategies. Future research should explore the long-term effects of personality traits on conflict management and the impact of targeted interventions on improving teacher relationships and student outcomes.

This study contributes to the understanding of how teachers' personality traits influence their conflict management styles within the Philippine educational context. The insights gained from this research can inform school administrators and policymakers in developing targeted interventions that support teachers in managing conflicts effectively. As the educational landscape continues to evolve, fostering a culture of collaboration and understanding among educators will be essential for enhancing the overall quality of education in the Philippines.

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